

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
மதிப்பாய்வு செய்யப்படும் இதழ்

Volume 1, Issue 2, May 2022

E-ISSN – XXXX-XXXX

Gender Discrimination in Shashi Deshpande's *The Dark Holds No Terror*

Dr. D. Saraswathi, Assistant Professor of English, Sri.S.R.N.M College, Sattur, Tamil Nadu, India.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4049-2532>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6801481

Abstract

Gender is a common term where Gender discrimination is meant only for women because females are the only victims of gender discrimination. In India, mostly women at a young age depending on their father, in the middle age-she depends on their husband, and in the older age-depend on their son. Women always depend on somebody for their livelihoods. Hence, independence in economical aspects is imperative for women's development. The novel The Dark Hold No Terrors explores the trauma of a middle-class working woman who has become a trap in a male-dominated society. Deshpande pictures her men and women characters as the victim of modern society. In this novel, Sarita (saru) is the female protagonist who narrates the story. Through her narration, we can understand her parents, dead brother Dhurva, her husband Manohar (manu), and her old teacher Boozie. She decides not to protest against the oppression quality openly by breaking her familial life.

Keywords: Gender Discrimination, Shashi Deshpande, *The Dark Holds No Terror*.

Gender discrimination is discrimination against a person or a group on the grounds of sex or gender identity. The word 'discrimination' means "unfair treatment of a person or group on the basis of prejudice". Socially, sexual difference has been used to justify cultures in which one sex or the other has been restricted to considerably inferior and secondary roles. We know that Gender is a common term Gender discrimination is meant only for women, because female are the only victims of gender discrimination. She is not only biologically but also socially determined. The proper and perpetuate efforts are taken to avoid these discrimination. The women are discriminated on the basis of denial of equality, rights and opportunity and suppression in any form on the basis of gender. The half of the world's populations is females. The two-third of work of the total work in the world are done by the female but received only one-tenth of the world's total income. The two-third of the women are illiterates but they have possessed only one percent of the total world's assets. It is a well known fact that India is a male dominant society and gender discrimination is customized habitually.

Berta Esteve-volart (2004) described that gender discrimination against women in the market place reduces the available talent in an economy It has negative economic consequences. It has many social practices seen as normal from a religious or culture point of view which have women out of the economic mainstream. These social practices may have profound economic consequences. They do not allow society to take advantage of the talent inherent in women. The male dominance is the origin of gender discrimination. In India a woman still needs the anchor of a husband and a family. The male domination nature has led women to walk with their head down. It was all practiced from the beginning and is followed till date. In parliament, the opposing parties believe that women are born to do house hold tasks and manage children and family. The women in the young age depends her father, in the middle age-she depends on her husband and in the older age-depend on her son. There is

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
மதிப்பாய்வு செய்யப்படும் இதழ்

Volume 1, Issue 2, May 2022

E-ISSN – XXXX-XXXX

always dependence on somebody for her livelihoods. Hence, independent in economical aspects are imperative for women's development. The decision making power of women is denied in the family as well as in the society. Mostly males make the importance decision in the family and in the society. This makes women as voiceless and destroys her self-confidence and she feels less important in the family as well as in the society. So to end gender discrimination women must empower with decision making power. Like male or even above them female plays important role in the family and national development. But her contribution is not recognized by the male dominated society.

Shashi Deshpande is an award winning novelist. Her novel usually have woman as the protagonists. This has led readers to call her a feminist writer. She is considered as one of the most accomplished contemporary Indian women writers in English. Deshpande is gifted with an inborn literary bent of mind which natured with her experiences in life. Shashi Deshpande is known for creating. The women characters in Deshpande's women protagonists are victim of the prevalent gross gender discrimination - first as daughter and later as wives. The novel *The Dark Hold No Terrors* throws light on the struggles of a middle class working woman who has become a trap in the male dominated society. There is a clear picture of her men and women characters as the victim of modern society. Sarita (saru) who is the female protagonist narrates the story. Through her narration we come across her parents, dead brother Dhurva, her husband Manohar (manu) and her old teacher Boozie. She is not ready to protest against the oppression quality openly through breaking her familial life.

The first half of *The Dark Hold No Terrors* deals with the unkind, vicious and prejudiced of Saru's mother. She is a strong product of patriarchal for her son's death. "why didn't you die? Why are you alive and he dead". (P.[14]) Saru undergoes gender discrimination at home even in her childhood. Saru's mother attitude is typical of most Indian mothers and Saru's problem is increased when the younger brother accidentally dies by drowning. It is a turning point in her life. Saru's mother's obvious preference for her brother, Dhruva, creates a sense of alienation within Saru. It produces a sense of insecurity.

I didn't truly, I didn't, It was an accident. I loved him, my little brother. I tried to save him. Truly I tried, but I couldn't. And I ran way yes, I ran way, I admit that but I didn't kill him (P. 146)

This difference in her mother's treatment of her son and daughter's enrages Saru. Being a traditional Hindu woman, the mother considers. It is her duty to remind her daughter that she is grown up and she should behave accordingly. It is a mother's responsibility to see that the children especially the daughters behave well. When Saru attains menarche, the first experience of menstruation is horrifying and painful to her. Instead of explaining the process to her and putting her at ease, the mother makes her fear with the fact that she would bleed for years. She is not allowed to enter the kitchen and puja-room. She is compelled to sleep on straw mat separate plate and tumbler is provided to her, which makes her feel like an outcast during those days. It is a great wonder for Saru that why the women is considered unholy during the menstruation period. She feels like an unwanted child who is perplexed at her very being.

Saru, the Indian girl-child is puzzled and panicky at the physical changes taking place within her body at the time of puberty. She feels repugnant and hideous. She is not happy with the growth of her body. She is warned that she is steeping into that difficult and shameful state of woman hood. Time and again Saru is made to realize that with physical growth, she has been vulnerable to the atrocious and ravenous clutches of the society. Time

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
மதிப்பாய்வு செய்யப்படும் இதழ்

Volume 1, Issue 2, May 2022

E-ISSN – XXXX-XXXX

and again she is made to realize that being girl she is different and not as privileged as a boy clearly indicating gender discrimination. It takes time for young, Saru to understand she was a female and some things are bound to happen.

Things fell, with a miraculous exactness, into place. I was a female. I was born that way, that was the way my body had to be, those were the things that had to happen to me. And that was that (P.63)

She rebels against her mother “if you are a woman, I don’t want to be one”(P.55), says Saru to her mother. The words of Saru reveal us her hatred for the life of a woman and on the basis of discrimination meted to women at large because of the patriarchal system. Saru’s first public defiance of the patriarchal power system is when she breaks the so called protective barrier of her house and leaves home. With a deep seated hurt feeling, she says to her mother, “you don’t want me to have anything; you don’t want me to do anything. You don’t even want me to live” (P.142). Bitterness and hatred for her mother drives her to leave home and obsessively seek success in medical college.

The whole novel is full of occurrences showing gender discrimination. Sarita’s mother shows detestation and bitterness towards her daughter and thinks that she too should have died when her son died. Sarita is not even recognized as daughter. The mother remarks: “...Daughter? I don’t have any daughter. I had a son and he died. Now I am childless” (P.196). Sarita’s brother, Dhruva’s disappearance in the pond and her father’s punishing the mother by not eating food cooked by her reminds Sarita a Sanskrit story from her school text where a woman did not disturb her husband’s sleep even to save her child from fire. Agni, the god of fire, had to come and save child. It suggests that woman was made to be the hand maid of man, whose work is only to wait on man. Gender discrimination is vividly displayed here. Saru wants to be recognized as a person than as a woman and she wants to have an independent social image. It makes Sarita extremely angry at gender discrimination and she thinks,

...who wrote that story? A man, of course. Telling all women for all time your duty to me comes first. And women poor feels, believed him. So even today dhruva’s mother considers it a punishment to be deprived of a chance to serve her husband.” (P.207).

The second half of the story deals with the Saru’s life as a wife. Saru undergoes gender discrimination as a wife too. She suffers the sexual torture of her husband, Manohar, (Manu) who thinks that being a male he has all rights to treat his wife as he wants. Saru’s introspection at her father’s home bring home answer to her question by her and for that she needs to voice her feeling. Manohar, Sarita’s husband is purely an “Indian man”. He is an underpaid college teacher. In the beginning their life was normal. In one of the interviews a female journalist asks Manu how does it feel when your wife earns not only butter but most of the bread as well? At that time he laughed with Saru. He makes fun of her. So, he feels pride manifest in the form of sexual sadism. Manu and Saru had planned for a trip to Ooty. While shopping they met Manu’s colleague and his wife. At that time Manu revealed their plan. So he was violent. He doesn’t behave like a husband in the privacy of their room at night but as a rapist. In this novel, women characters dominate the men characters. So Deshpande tries to bring justice to her female characters. The female character shares a lot about the suffering, their inner trauma, victim of marital rape, the silence of the male character conveys about their dilemma, suffering inferiority and male adjustment.

As a consequence of the treatment meted at home and in a bid to search for her identity, Saru resolves to be a doctor, hoping that a professional career could be the key that

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
மதிப்பாய்வு செய்யப்படும் இதழ்

Volume 1, Issue 2, May 2022

E-ISSN – XXXX-XXXX

would unlock the door out of the wretched life at home. Whether it is her profession or marriage, Sarita had to put up with the opposition of her mother. Her defiance is expressed when she becomes economically independent and marries a man of her own choice. “women, in order to achieve freedom, seek marriage as an alternative to the bondage created by the parental family. Saru resents the role of a daughter and looks forward to the role of wife, with the hope that her new role will help in winning freedom”.

She hopes that the role of a wife will give her relief from oppression of the mother, and will give her freedom from this gender discrimination which she was not able to understand or tolerate. Her married life with Manu had its own ups and downs and it makes her think that even pleasure is a fantasy where as grief seems more real having mass and mother. The departure of Saru from her mother makes her to step into autonomy. Manu cannot tolerate people greeting her and ignoring him. The gender discrimination continues even in the professional arena. Saru being a lady doctor is preferred by all. She gets respect and her husband can't digest that. This changes the loving husband into a sadist. Saru feels a gradual disappearance of love which she had once developed for Manu. She starts hating the man-woman relationship which is based on attraction and need, not love.

Manu's sexual overtures hurt the woman in Saru. She cannot free herself from him as she lives in a concrete society. Moreover, the next morning after the night's ordeal, he used to be the same smiling Manu again which Saru is not able to understand or digest. As a man Manu had the liberty to treat his wife the way he wanted, even to the brink of marital rape. But Saru being a woman could not stop his overtures or even complain about it.

The hurting hands, the savage teeth the monstrous assault of a horrible familiar's body.
And above me a face I could not recognize”.(P.112)

Deshpande explores the strain and anguish of being a woman. She concentrates on woman's pursuit to find out her true worth. It doesn't take long for Saru to realize that her coming to her parental home after she gets to know about her mother's death and to seek refuge from her husband was a futile exercise as she is not welcome there; being a daughter she is expected to be happily parked with her husband. In the end of the novel when Saru is informed about Manu's arrival to her paternal home to take her back she is disturbed initially as she is totally upset about her relationship and does not want to take him. The moment she realizes the importance of life, she resolves to take charge of her life.

Deshpande draws the role of women and men of middle class family where the female protagonists are highly qualified, courageous and strong in the male dominated society. The realization that Saru gets after nearly a fortnight's stay in her father's house is that it is her life that she is living and she has to have all the hurdles herself. She has to live for her own happiness by forgetting all about the past. “it is my life and I have rights to live in my own way”. She gets the courage to face the dark. The dark wherein she was subjugated to physical and mental torture by her husband. She knows that *The Dark Hold No Terrors* if she rises to face it. The positive note in the climax of the novel matured Saru. She will do everything possible and not to let the gender discrimination come in the way of her happiness. She will fight it out and makes her life better.

References

- [1] Deshpande, Shashi, *The Dark Holds No Terrors*, Penguin Books, New Delhi. 1980.
- [2] Beauvoir, Simone De *'The Second Sex'* translated and edited by H.M.Parshily, Placodon

பாண்டியன் மகளிர் ஆய்வு இதழ்
மதிப்பாய்வு செய்யப்படும் இதழ்

Volume 1, Issue 2, May 2022

E-ISSN – XXXX-XXXX

Classics Edition published 1988 by Pan Books Ltd. Cavage Place London.
[3]Singh Jyoti. *Indian Women Novelists: Feminist Physiological Study*. Jaipur: Rawat Publications, 2007.

Author Contribution Statement: NIL.

Author Acknowledgement: NIL.

Author Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> International License.